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Human Influenza Vaccine Composition

An advisory group of experts, convened by the WHO Global Influenza Programme, analyze biannually influenza virus surveillance data generated by the Global Influenza Surveillance and Response System (GISRS) and issues formal recommendation for the composition of influenza vaccines for either northern or southern hemisphere influenza seasons.

High yield candidate vaccine viruses are developed by collaboration of laboratories involved in developing reassortants and WHO Collaborating Centres (CCs).

Once developed, these candidate reassortants are sent to WHO CCs for characterization of their antigenic and genetic properties before being released to interested institutions on request. Reference reagents are subsequently developed and standardized by Essential Regulatory Laboratories (ERLs), in collaboration with vaccine manufacturers.

26 February 2021

Recommended composition of influenza virus vaccines for use in the 2021-2022 northern hemisphere influenza season.

It is recommended that **quadrivalent influenza vaccines** for use in the 2021 - 2022 northern hemisphere influenza season contain the following:

Egg-based Vaccines

- an A/Victoria/2570/2019 ([H1N1](#))pdm09-like virus; (EPI_ISL_417210)
- an A/Cambodia/e0826360/2020 ([H3N2](#))-like virus; (EPI_ISL_806547)
- a B/Washington/02/2019 ([B/Victoria](#) lineage)-like virus; (EPI_ISL_352076) and
- a B/Phuket/3073/2013 ([B/Yamagata](#) lineage)-like virus. (EPI_ISL_168822)

Cell- or recombinant-based Vaccines

- an A/Wisconsin/588/2019 ([H1N1](#))pdm09-like virus; (EPI_ISL_404460)
- an A/Cambodia/e0826360/2020 ([H3N2](#))-like virus; (EPI_ISL_944639)
- a B/Washington/02/2019 ([B/Victoria](#) lineage)-like virus; (EPI_ISL_347829) and
- a B/Phuket/3073/2013 ([B/Yamagata](#) lineage)-like virus. (EPI_ISL_161843)

It is recommended that **trivalent influenza vaccines** for use in the 2021-2022 northern hemisphere influenza season contain the following:

Egg-based Vaccines

- an A/Victoria/2570/2019 ([H1N1](#))pdm09-like virus; (EPI_ISL_417210)
- an A/Cambodia/e0826360/2020 ([H3N2](#))-like virus; (EPI_ISL_806547) and
- a B/Washington/02/2019 ([B/Victoria](#) lineage)-like virus. (EPI_ISL_352076)

Cell- or recombinant-based Vaccines

- an A/Wisconsin/588/2019 ([H1N1](#))pdm09-like virus; (EPI_ISL_404460)
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